

SOME VIEWS ON THE TOPIC OF HYPOCORISMS AS THE VOCATIVE FORM IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Tabassum Khalilova

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Linguistics (English language) Masters degree student

E-mail: smilegrin08@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on using hypocorism as vocative forms in the English and Uzbek languages. Hypocorisms are used when the speaker and listener are known each other. Especially, hypocorisms are used among relatives, family members and friends to call or address. While calling or addressing to someone or something, the hypocorisms are used as vocatives.

Keywords: hypocorism, diminutive, vocative, vocative form, call, address, name.

Hypocorisms are frequently utilized as forms of address, much like other diminutive structures derived from words that signify particular groups of individuals, such as gender and age labels, familial terms, and expressions representing various forms of social engagement. Consequently, vocatives, being a special category in Turkic languages [4.329]. So what is hypocorism itself? It is a shorter form of a word or given name. According to Wikipedia, it may be a diminutive form of a person's name, such as *Izzy* for Isabel or *Bob* for Robert, or it may be unrelated. People's names are shortened as a result of emphatic lengthening of vowel sounds. This possesses calling intonation. Under the influence of the calling intonation, some conditions occur like personal names are shortened, lengthened, and some sounds are dropped. People's names which are pronounced shortened, are considered a new type of vocative form [2.197].

As a result of the shortening of the names, usually, the first syllable is used. For example: *Zarnigor-Zar*

In some cases, this can be show respect. Moreover, it expresses the closeness of the speaker to the listener, intimate connection, the meaning of endearment. According to their lexical meaning and syntactic morphological function, shortened names such as *Bill* (english), *Shoqi* (uzbek) looks like an address used to call animals [1.95]. Shortened people's names occurs through various phonetic phenomena. They can give the same meaning even if they are shortened.

According to Urinbayev's opinion the shortening of the names of the people in language must have come as a result of such a demand, that is, to create a comfort in the appeal [5.49]. The names can be shortened differently according to individuum's speech.

For example: The name Muhammad is shortened in differently: Mamat, Mad or O'rinoy- O'rin, etc.

In addition, one of the reasons for shortening of personal names is dialogic speech. Because in dialogic speech we, also, find expressive forms of assessment. They are used as vocative words. Emotive words, that is, abbreviated nouns gives the meaning of urging, calling and appealing. Vocative words used in dialogical speech are often found in letter style.

How to use shortened people's names depends on the attitude of the speaker. In Uzbek, such situation is used when the speaker and listener at the same age or addressing older people to younger ones. In English culture, hypocorism is commonly used among different age of people.

Sometimes hypocorism can involve modifying a name, with the possibility of shortening it. In English culture, the names *Ted*, *Jack*, and *Bob* are created as hypocoristic versions of *Edward*, *John*, and *Robert*. This alteration may result in a name that is only partially similar to the original name. For example, *Hal* and *Hank* are both used as shortened forms of the name Henry [6]. This kind of cases can also be found in Uzbek names: *Begi*, *Bek* for *Diyorbek*, *Begim*, *Murod* for *Bekmurod*, *Zulash*, *Zulay* for *Zulayho* etc.

One of the way to create a form of endearment for a name is through the use of a diminutive, which alters the name to convey smallness. In English, this is often achieved by adding the suffixes "-ie" or "-y" to the name. For example, John can become *Johnny* or *Johnnie*. The diminutive may also be created from a previously altered version of the name that has undergone one of the aforementioned changes. As an illustration, *Timothy* and *William* can be transformed into *Timmy* and *Billy* [6]. In Uzbek, this is often achieved by adding the suffixes "-(a)y", "(a)v" or "-(i)m" to the name [5.53]. For example:

-(a)y: *Ibrohim-Ibay*, *Salohiddin- Salay*, etc. In that case the they are used as address and appeal;

-(i)m: *Ro'zimat-Ro'zim*, *Miraziz-Azizim*, etc. In that case the names used as endearment.

-(a)v: *Bahouddin- Bahov*, *Kamolliddin- Kamov*, etc. This is not commonly used, in some dialects it can be used. When it is used, the meaning will be call, cares.

Omitting –a sound (only for girl's name): *Gulnoza-Gulnoz*, *Gulzoda-Gulzod*, etc. But there is such girls' names which ends –a, cannot be shortened by omitting, because

in that case, they show gender. This kind of names, especially, are made by adding –a for boys’ name:

Aziz-Aziza, Azim-Azima, Dilshod-Dilshoda,, Laziz-Laziza, Latif-Latifa, Habib Habiba, Nodir-Nodira, Muslim-Muslima, Diyor-Diyora, Ziyod-Ziyoda, Komil-Komila, Naim-Naima, Said-Saida, Shahzod-Shahzoda, Shoir-Shoira, Ozod-Ozoda, Umid-Umida, etc.

Actually, when a person’s name is shortened to a more affectionate or casual version, it typically suggests some level of closeness. For instance, a man named James may be called *Jim or Jimmy* by his loved ones rather than by someone unfamiliar or in a professional setting. These shortened versions of names are often used when speaking to children, but can also be used between adults to convey warmth or familiarity.

Some hypocoristic names for objects are based on the way small children talk or on the the simplified, higher-pitched form of speech often used by parents with small children. Use of the diminutives “doggy” and “kitty” to refer to dogs and cats are a common examples. In Uzbek this occurs to adding “–cha” suffix of the noun: “mushukcha”, “kuchukcha”.

As well as giving positive meaning of the names, in some cases this may be negative meaning. Using a shortened or childlike version of someone’s name in unfamiliar situations can be considered impolite, disrespectful, or demeaning. In certain languages, using diminutives outside of a friendly context can even be seen as an insult because it suggests that the person being addressed is inferior or undeserving of respect. Additionally, using a hypocoristic form of a woman’s name in a formal setting is often viewed as dismissive.

CONCLUSION

So, as a result of shortening of the people’s name, the vocative forms can exist. This happens as a result of a number of factors:

1. Intonation, especially calling intonation, the omitting of vowel in names ;
2. As a result of to create comfort in speech;
3. Various relationships of the speaker to the hearer, including friendship.

REFERENCES:

1. Дугуров П. В. (1960) Междометия как особый разряд слов - Автореферат канд. дисс. - Москва.
2. Гвоздев. А. (1961) Новый Современный русский литературный язык. – Москва.
3. Шмелев. Д. Н. (1960) Архаические формы в современном русском языке. - Москва.
4. Юлдашев А.А. (1956) Звательные слова в тюркских языках. - Москва.
5. Urinbayev B. (1972) “Hozirgi o‘zbek tilida vokativlar” - Tashkent.
6. <https://www.languagehumanities.org/what-is-a-hypocorism.htm>